

Technical Note on Quality Assessment for Vision-1 (SSTL S1-4)

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
0.1	02 November 2020	First draft for ESA review
0.2	13 May 2021	Second draft for ESA review
1.0	07 July 2021	First issue

1. INTRODUCTION

This technical note details the results of the (preliminary) mission data quality assessments (including geometric calibration, radiometric calibration and image quality) performed on a sample of orthorectified bundle products generated for *Vision-1*, a relatively new addition to the Airbus Earth Observation (EO) portfolio of commercial optical missions.

The aforementioned mission data quality assessments are performed in accordance with the assessment guidelines, detailed in [RD-1, RD-2], that constitute the European Space Agency (ESA) Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) Project's *EO Mission Data Quality Assessment Framework*. An important representation of the latter framework, constructed by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), is what is known as the *maturity matrix*. It is a diagrammatic summary of the following:

- **Documentation Review:** *the EDAP Optical team reviews materials (e.g. data and documentation) provided by the data provider or operator, some of which may not be publically available, or even the scientific community (e.g. published papers). The results are detailed in Section 3 (covering the first four columns of the maturity matrix).*
- **Data Quality Assessments:** *the EDAP Optical team performs data quality assessments (i.e. validation assessments), independently of any validation assessments performed by the data provider and / or operator. The results are detailed in Section 4 (covering the last column, 'Validation', of the maturity matrix).*

The above assessments are performed by the EDAP Optical team using the appropriate in-house and open-source ad-hoc scripts / tools.

It is important to note the purpose of the aforementioned framework is to ensure that the delivered commercial mission data is fit for purpose and that all decisions regarding the inclusion of the commercial mission as an ESA third party mission can be made fairly and with confidence.

1.1 Reference Documents

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v1.2, September 2019.
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework – Optical Guidelines, EDAP.REP.002, v2.0, December 2020.
- RD-3. Airbus - Vision-1 Imagery: User Guide, v1.0, April 2020.
- RD-4. Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., et al. 2016 The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018. (doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18)
- RD-5. Airbus – OneAtlas Basemap Specification, v1.0, May 2018.
- RD-6. Airbus – WorldDEM4Ortho Technical Product Specification, v1.4, July 2018.

- RD-7. Airbus – DIMAP Format. Online: <https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/en/8722-the-dimap-format>. Accessed: October 2020.
- RD-8. M. Cournet, A. Giros, L. Dumas, J.M. Delvit., D. Greslou, F. Languille, G. Blanchet, S. May, and J. Michel (2016). 2D Sub-Pixel Disparity Measurement Using QPEC / Medicis, Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLI-B1, 291-298, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLI-B1-291-2016.
- RD-9. Bouvet, M.; Thome, K.; Berthelot, B.; Bialek, A.; Czapla-Myers, J.; Fox, N.P.; Goryl, P.; Henry, P.; Ma, L.; Marcq, S.; Meygret, A.; Wenny, B.N.; Woolliams, E.R. RadCalNet: A Radiometric Calibration Network for Earth Observing Imagers Operating in the Visible to Shortwave Infrared Spectral Range. Remote Sens. 2019, 11, 2401, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11202401>
- RD-10. CEOS, RadCalNet Quick Start Guide. July 2018 https://www.radcalnet.org/resources/RadCalNetQuickstartGuide_20180702.pdf
- RD-11. S2 MPC – L1C Data Quality Report, S2-PDGS-MPC-DQR-55, Is. 55, September 2020. Online: <https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/685211/Sentinel-2-L1C-Data-Quality-Report-September-2020.pdf>.
- RD-12. Françoise Viallefont-Robinet, Dennis Helder, Renaud Fraise, Amy Newbury, Frans van den Bergh, Donghan Lee, Sébastien Saunier.. Comparison of MTF measurements using edge method: towards reference data set. Optics Express, Optical Society of America, 2018, 26 (26), pp.33625-33648. (hal-02055611)
- RD-13. S. Saunier, P. Goryl, G. Chander, M. Bouvet, R. Santer and S. Kocaman, “Radiometric, geometric and image quality assessment of the ALOS AVNIR-2 and PRISM sensors,” TGRS, 48(10), 3855-3866 (2010).
- RD-14. K. Kohm, “Modulation transfer function measurement method and results for the Orbview-3 high resolution imaging satellite,” Proceedings of ISPRS, Istanbul, Turkey (2004).

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

AC	Across-track
AL	Along-track
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
BRDF	bidirectional reflectance distribution function
CEOS	Committee for Earth Observation Satellites
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DIMAP	Digital Image Map
EDAP	Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot

EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GCP	ground control points
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
IFOV	Instantaneous Field of View
IVOS	Infrared and Visible Optical Sensors
LSF	Line Spread Function
MS	multispectral
MSI	Multispectral Instrument
MTF	Modulation Transfer Function
NIIRS	National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale
NPL	National Physical Laboratory
PAN	panchromatic
PICS	Pseudo-Invariant Calibration Site
RER	Relative Edge Response
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
VHR	Very High Resolution
WGCV	Working Group for Calibration and Validation

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The operation of the **Vision-1** sensor provides the user community with Very High Resolution (**VHR**) imagery (multispectral (**MS**) and panchromatic (**PAN**)) of the Earth's surface. The geometric, radiometric and image quality of the aforementioned imagery has been assessed, using a small sample of orthorectified bundle products provided by the data provider and operator, Airbus, and the results are summarised in Table 2-1.

(Note the sample of orthorectified bundle products used for the following assessments were delivered to the EDAP optical team between April and October 2020.)

Table 2-1: Vision-1 Assessment Area Results

Assessment Area	Results
<p>All mission minimum requirements specified in this technical note are detailed in the mission user guide [RD-3].</p>	
<p>Geometric Calibration Quality</p>	<p>Pixel Size / Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) @ Nadir – Panchromatic 0.87 / 0.87 m, Multispectral 3.5 / 3.48 m.</p> <p>1. Absolute Geolocation (Planimetric) Accuracy</p> <p>The absolute geolocation accuracy of the panchromatic imagery is approximately 4.20 m CE90 (RMSE 3.23 m), which meets the minimum requirement, specified by the data provider, of < 12.00 m CE90 @ nadir.</p> <p>The absolute geolocation accuracy of the multispectral imagery is approximately 12.07 m CE90 (RMSE 7.55 m). Note the product imagery used to assess the latter has a viewing angle (off-nadir) < 10°.</p> <p>2. Temporal Geolocation (Planimetric) Accuracy</p> <p>The temporal geolocation accuracy of the panchromatic imagery is approximately 4.08 m CE90 (RMSE 2.95 m). Note no minimum requirement has been specified by the data provider.</p> <p>The temporal geolocation accuracy of the multispectral imagery is approximately 6.15 m CE90 (RMSE 4.14 m). Note no minimum requirement has been specified by the data provider.</p> <p>Note the temporal geolocation accuracies detailed above are determined from only two products, sensed nearly ten months apart, and so should be considered with caution. The latter should be more accurately determined using a larger sample of products.</p> <p>3. Band Co-registration Accuracy</p>

	<p>The band co-registration accuracies of this sensor's blue-green, green-red and red-near-infrared band pairs is 0.22, 0.23 and 0.36 multispectral pixels CE90, respectively. This result, along with the determined uncertainty budget, indicates the minimum requirement of < 0.3 multispectral pixels CE90, specified by the data provider, has been met for all multispectral band pairs (the lower last band pair co-registration accuracy is expected, due to slightly poorer image matching with the near-infrared band).</p> <p>The band co-registration accuracies of this sensor's blue-panchromatic and near-infrared-panchromatic band pairs are 0.55 and 0.40 multispectral CE90, respectively. This result indicates the minimum requirement of < 0.3 multispectral pixels CE90 has not been met but this is most likely due to the error introduced when the geometrically resampled panchromatic image, resampled to match the multispectral image (grid), is used in panchromatic-multispectral image matching.</p>
<p>Radiometric Calibration Quality</p>	<p>1. Absolute Radiometric Accuracy</p> <p>The absolute radiometric accuracies of the multispectral bands are blue < 4.60 %, green < 5.03 %, red < 6.11 %, near-infrared < 7.66 % and panchromatic < 4.60 % bands, <u>without</u> bi-directional reflectance distribution corrections applied. The latter absolute radiometric accuracies are higher <u>with</u> the application of bi-directional reflectance distribution corrections, as expected, and are within the minimum requirement, specified by the data provider, of blue / green / red < 5.9 %, near-infrared < 6.2 % and panchromatic < 6 %.</p> <p>Note the latter result is supported by the higher accuracies indicated through cross-validation with reference multispectral measurement data from Sentinel-2B.</p> <p>2. Temporal Radiometric Accuracy</p> <p>The temporal radiometric accuracy of all bands appears to be stable (i.e. no temporal degradation of radiometric calibration) over the period observed.</p>
<p>Image Quality</p>	<p>1. Signal-to-Noise Ratio</p> <p>The signal-to-noise ratios for all multispectral and panchromatic bands has been calculated and compared to the signal-to-noise ratios, accompanied by mean radiances, detailed in [RD-3] – the ratios are satisfactory (blue 165:1, green 139:1, red 115:1, near-infrared 111:1 and panchromatic 222:1) and stable. However, the ratios are lower than stated in the [RD-3] (reason not known but may be due to the reference source used, method, pre-launch values, etc.).</p> <p>2. Modular Transfer Function</p>

	<p>The results of this assessment on the panchromatic band, whose spatial resolution was deemed suitable for the artificial target used, indicate the minimum requirement of panchromatic modulation transfer function > 10 % has been met.</p> <p>(The full-width half-maximum, which is used to quantify the spatial resolution of an image, indicates a spatial resolution of 1.58 m (across-track) x 1.73 m (along-track)).</p> <p>Note the artificial target used here was not suitable for the assessment of the multispectral bands due to their lower spatial resolution.</p> <p>3. Image Interpretability</p> <p>The sensor's multispectral and panchromatic imagery appears to be of a slightly better quality than that of the reference sensor's (Pléiades) imagery, based on factors such as improved contrast and improved delineation of objects / features of interest.</p>
<p>Visual Inspections</p>	<p>1. Visual Inspection</p> <p>The visual inspection of imagery from a sample of products did not reveal any gross anomalies or artefacts.</p>

Figure 2-1: Vision-1 Panchromatic Imagery over La Crau (France). Scale 1:2175.

3. VISION-1 DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENTS

3.1 EDAP Maturity Matrix

Table 3-1: Vision-1 Quality Maturity Matrix

Product Information	Product Generation	Ancillary Information	Uncertainty Characterisation	Validation	Key
Product Details 	Reference Data Representativeness	Not Assessed			
Product Availability & Accessibility 	Reference Data Quality	Not Assessable			
Product Format 	Validation Method	Basic			
User Documentation 	Validation Results	Intermediate			
Metrological Traceability Documentation					Good

 Information not public

3.1.1 Product Information

The sensor product type being assessed here is the orthorectified bundle product which provides multispectral and panchromatic imagery (16-bit encoded), from the same acquisition (pushbroom sensor, strip / mono acquisition mode), in a single product. These sensor products may be considered as ready-to-use products.

Product Details	
Product Name	<i>Vision-1 Bundle Standard Orthorectified</i>
Sensor Name	<i>Vision-1 (S1-4 Satellite)</i>
Sensor Type	<i>Optical – Multispectral and Panchromatic</i>
Mission Type	<i>Single Satellite (Airbus Intelligence Constellation)</i>
Mission Orbit	<i>Sun-synchronous (10:30 AM descending node, 583 km altitude)</i>
Product Version Number	<i>Processor: Keystone v4.7.x <</i>
Product ID	<i>VIS1_BUN_ORTP</i>
Product Processing Level	<i>Level 1C (Standard Orthorectified) (Metadata and documentation contain calibration coefficients for conversion from digital numbers to top-of-atmosphere reflectances)</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Digital Numbers (DN) / Spectral Radiance</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>DN / W.st¹.m².µm⁻¹</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>Radiometric Quality: Red / Green / Blue < 5.9 %, NIR < 6.2 %, PAN < 6.0 % Geometric Quality: Planimetric - CE90 < 12.0 m @ Nadir</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>Very High Resolution Multispectral: 3.48 m GSD (3.50 m Pixel Size) Panchromatic: 0.87 m GSD (0.87 m Pixel Size) Full Swath Width @ Nadir: 20.8 km</i>
Spatial Coverage	<i>Global (Orbital Inclination 97.5°)</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>Revisit < 1 – 8 Days (Latitude Dependent)</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>Mission Lifetime > 7 Years</i>
Point of Contact	<i>ukintelligence-imagerysupport@airbus.com</i>
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>The sensor products are made available upon request only (orders / tasks are placed with the data provider's imagery support team: +44 (0) 01483 446960, ukintelligence-imagerysupport@airbus.com).</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>The standard license for imagery, adapted on a case-by-case basis (i.e. depending upon the needs of the user), is delivered to the customer by the Airbus U.K Data Services team (contact e-mail address provided above).</i>

Limitations on public access	<i>No public access.</i>
Product Abstract	<i>None.</i>

All required product information (included in product metadata, documentation, etc.) is provided, with only some recommended product information missing (e.g. product abstract), and therefore the status of **Product Details** in the maturity matrix has been graded as “Good”.

Availability & Accessibility	
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>The product information (included in product metadata, etc.) provided meets some of the FAIR principles only.</i>
Data Management Plan	<i>None.</i>
Availability Status	<i>The sensor products are made available upon request only (orders / tasks are placed with the data provider’s imagery support team: +44 (0) 01483 446960, ukintelligence-imagerysupport@airbus.com).</i>

The product information (included in product metadata, documentation, etc.) provided does not meet all Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (**FAIR**) Principles [RD-4], which typically takes the form of a detailed data catalogue or API, and so as there is no data management plan that demonstrates progress towards the FAIR principles either, the status of **Availability and Accessibility** in the maturity matrix has been graded as “Basic”.

Product Format	
Product File Format	<p><i>The sensor product format adopted is the Digital Image Map (DIMAP) format. This product format, which is not a proprietary product format, has been designed to describe geographic data, such as sensor imagery (raster), comprehensively. This product format, described in [RD-3] and [RD-6], ensure the following bundle product content:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Product Multispectral / Panchromatic GeoTIFF (.TIF)</i> • <i>Product Multispectral / Panchromatic GeoTIFF Georeference Metadata (.TFW)</i> • <i>Product Metadata (.XML)</i> • <i>Product Metadata (.HTML)</i> • <i>Product Preview Image (.TIF, .KMZ)</i> • <i>Product Preview Image Icon (.JPG)</i> <p><i>Note rational polynomial coefficients are provided with the projected product type only, for simple orthorectification, and / or other forms of geometric processing, by the user if required.</i></p>
Metadata Conventions	<i>DIMAP (v1.0, encoding ISO-8859-1)</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

The product format is of a well-documented standard file format, which also uses community naming convention standards, but as it is not considered as Analysis Ready

Data, as defined by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (**CEOS**), the status of **Product Format** in the maturity matrix has been graded as “Good”.

User Documentation		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Vision-1 User Guide	<i>This user guide [RD-3] accompanies data delivery.</i>	No
ATBD	<i>Documentation not made available to users.</i>	N/A

The current user documentation includes a detailed user guide, which also contains some high-level information that would typically be found in an Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (**ATBD**) (formal document not made available), and so the status of **User Documentation** in the maturity matrix has been graded as “Intermediate”.

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Document Reference	<i>Documentation not made available to users.</i>
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	<i>Documentation not made available to users.</i>

There is no documentation available on the traceability chain / uncertainty tree and so the status of **Metrological Traceability Documentation** in the maturity matrix has been graded as ‘Not Assessable’.

3.1.2 Product Generation

Sensor Calibration and Characterisation – Pre-Flight	
Summary	<i>The detailed (formal) pre-flight sensor calibration and characterisation (radiometric, spectral and spatial) information / documentation is not made available to users but some, very high-level information on the subject is mentioned in [RD-3], including characterising photo or pixel response non-uniformity, transmission losses (e.g. optics, filters), dark signal, relative gain, relative spectral response, etc.</i>
References	<i>[RD-3]</i>

The public information / documentation available on pre-flight sensor calibration and characterisation is rather limited and so ‘fit for purpose’ cannot be entirely assessed. Therefore, the status of **Pre-flight Sensor Calibration and Characterisation** in the maturity matrix has been graded as ‘Basic’.

Sensor Calibration and Characterisation – Post-Launch	
Summary	<i>The detailed (formal) post-launch sensor calibration and characterisation (radiometric, spectral and spatial) information / documentation is not made available to users but some, very high-level information on the subject is mentioned in [RD-3], including characterising transmission losses (e.g. optics, filters),</i>

	<i>dark signal, relative gain, etc. Note the latter characterisations are monitored at regular intervals throughout the satellite's life.</i>
References	<i>[RD-3]</i>

The public information / documentation available on post-launch sensor calibration and characterisation is rather limited and so 'fit for purpose' cannot be entirely assessed. Therefore, the status of **Post-launch Sensor Calibration and Characterisation** in the maturity matrix has been graded as '*Basic*'.

Additional Processing	
<i>Additional Processing 1</i>	
Description	<i>Orthorectification</i>
Reference	<i>[RD-3], [RD-6]</i>

The information / documentation available on or relevant to orthorectification can be found in *[RD-3]* and *[RD-6]* and so the status of **Additional Processing** in the maturity matrix has been graded as '*Good*'.

3.1.3 Ancillary Information

Product Flags	
Product Flag Documentation	<i>Not applicable as products do not contain flags.</i>
Comprehensiveness of Flags	<i>Not applicable as products do not contain flags.</i>

The products do not contain product flags and so the status of **Product Flags** in the maturity matrix has been graded as '*Not assessable*'.

Ancillary Data	
Ancillary Data Documentation	<i>The product-specific ancillary data (e.g. viewing and solar geometry angles, longitude, latitude, altitude), used to define measurements, can be found in product metadata and general ancillary data can be found in the accompanying documentation (e.g. user guide, other documentation requested from the data provider). However, uncertainties have not been quantified, where applicable, for all ancillary data.</i>
Comprehensiveness of Data	<i>Not applicable</i>
Uncertainty Quantified	<i>Not applicable.</i>

All ancillary data that is required to define and interpret measurements (including the quantification of uncertainty where applicable) per-product, not per-pixel, is provided in the product metadata and accompanying documentation and so **Ancillary Data** of the maturity matrix has been graded as '*Intermediate*'.

3.1.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

Uncertainty Characterisation Method	
Summary	<i>The methods used to characterise the uncertainties associated with geometric and radiometric performance are not included in the documentation made available to users.</i>
Reference	<i>Documentation not made available to users.</i>

The public information / documentation on uncertainty characterisation methods used are not made available to users and so **Uncertainty Characterisation Methods** of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Not Assessable'.

Uncertainty Sources Included	
Summary	<i>The information / documentation concerning the resources used in geometric processing (i.e. reference imagery and digital elevation model resources) is made available to users.</i>
Reference	<i>[RD-3], [RD-5], [RD-6]</i>

The public information / documentation on some of the sources of uncertainty associated with geometric performance only are provided and so **Uncertainty Sources Included** of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.

Uncertainty Values Provided	
Summary	<i>The documentation provides single uncertainty values that are used to characterise geometric and radiometric performance for the mission as a whole (i.e. rather than per product or per pixel).</i>
Reference	<i>[RD-3], [RD-5], [RD-6]</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

The uncertainty values that are used to characterise geometric calibration (including per-product uncertainty values), radiometric calibration and image quality are only single values for the mission as a whole and so **Uncertainty Values Provided** of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Basic'.

Geolocation Uncertainty	
Summary	<p><i>A single geolocation uncertainty value, in the form of circular error at a given confidence level, is documented in the user guide for the whole mission. The latter uncertainty value should take into consideration the uncertainty values associated with the relevant resources used in geometric processing, including reference imagery (e.g. basemap) and digital elevation model, which are also documented.</i></p> <p><i>Note product metadata provides geolocation uncertainty values, in the form of root mean square errors (in both directions) and circular errors (at 90 and 95 percentiles) also, per-product but</i></p>

	<i>this value does not appear to be determined using independent control points (i.e. control points that are not used to improve positioning accuracy / geolocation) and so cannot be considered reliable, or fit for purpose, especially where relatively few ground control points are used.</i>
Reference	[RD-3], [RD-5], [RD-6]

The geolocation uncertainty value(s) provided appear to include dependency on several other variables (including viewing angle, uncertainty propagated from resources, etc.), based on the information / documentation made available to users, and so **Geolocation Uncertainty** of the maturity matrix has been graded as “*Intermediate*”.

3.1.5 Validation

It is important to note this section, relating to the ‘Validation’ column of the maturity matrix, is based on the results of the data quality assessments performed by the EDAP Optical team **only** (i.e. **independently** of any data quality assessments performed by the data provider and / or operator).

Reference Data Representativeness	
Summary	<i>The representativeness of used reference sensor data, against which this sensor data is compared against, is good but the variety of reference data is small compared with the reference sensor data available (i.e. data from a variety of sensors with similar characteristics).</i>
Reference	None.

The representativeness of the reference data used is good but as the sample used is small and the variety limited, compared with the reference data available, **Reference Data Representativeness** of the maturity matrix has been graded as ‘*Basic*’.

Reference Data Quality & Suitability	
Summary	<i>The satellite data used as reference for some of the radiometric calibration assessments of Vision-1 is Sentinel-2A’s Multispectral Instrument that is well calibrated and documented. In addition to satellite data, in-situ reference data is provided by the well-established and documented RadCalNet.</i> <i>The satellite data used as reference for the geometric calibration assessments is SPOT-5 data whose geolocation accuracy has been validated by CNES as 2.5 m.</i>
Reference	[RD-9], [RD-10], [RD-11]

The reference data quality and suitability used by EDAP comes with a single uncertainty value for the entire sensor mission and so **Reference Data Quality** of the maturity matrix has been graded as ‘*Intermediate*’.

Validation Method	
Summary	<i>The validation methods used to assess image quality, geometric calibration and radiometric calibration are all well-documented and used by the scientific community (and are confirmed fit for purpose as the results produced are in alignment with what is expected / minimum requirements specified).</i>
Reference	[RD-9], [RD-10], NIIRS (https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm),

The validation methods used by EDAP produce simple uncertainty values (estimated from a statistical point of view) and so **Validation Method** of the maturity matrix has been graded as 'Intermediate'.

Validation Results	
Summary	<i>The validation results of all assessments are summarised in Section 2.</i>
Reference	See Section 4 and 5.

The validation results of the EDAP assessments, performed independently of the data provider, are in good agreement with this sensor and reference sensor (where applicable) measurements as well as with the uncertainty values claimed by the provider. Therefore, **Validation Results** of the maturity matrix has been graded as "Good".

4. DETAILED VISION-1 DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENTS

4.1 Objectives

The objectives of this work is to assess all core aspects of sensor data quality (geometric calibration, radiometric calibration, image quality) against sensor and product requirements or specifications, using the sample of sensor products provided.

4.2 Geometric Calibration Quality

This section describes the assessment of geometric calibration quality, implemented by the processing chain, of sensor products in terms of **absolute geolocation accuracy**, **temporal geolocation accuracy** and **band co-registration accuracy**.

4.2.1 Geometric Calibration and Orthorectification Resources

The geometric corrections (calibration) applied to sensor imagery during processing are determined by the geometric sensor model that uses important metadata (attitude, ephemeris and time), as well as ground control points extracted from sensor imagery that has been successfully matched with reference imagery, for refined geometric corrections (i.e. improved pointing accuracy), as input. The sensor imagery is then orthorectified using the rational polynomial coefficients, defining the geometric sensor model's orientation, and a digital elevation model.

4.2.1.1 Reference Imagery

The reference imagery used to extract the aforementioned ground control points for geometric refinement is provided by the **Airbus One Atlas BaseMap** resource [RD-5]. The construction and specification of this resource is detailed in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Airbus One Atlas Basemap Information

Parameter	Value	
Spatial Resolution	1.5 m Globally (SPOT) , 0.5 m Cities (Pléiades)	
Geolocation Accuracy	10.0 m CE90 (Absolute)	
	Regular Areas @ 90 % Confidence	Difficult Areas @ 75 % Confidence
Angle (Incidence)	< 20.0°	< 30.0°
Cloud	< 5.0 % Globally, < 2.0 % Cities	< 25.0 % Globally, < 10.0 % Cities
Age	< 1 Year	<2 Years

4.2.1.2 Digital Elevation Model

The Digital Elevation Model (**DEM**) used for orthorectification is provided by the **Airbus WorldDem4Ortho** resource [RD-6]. This resource has been optimised specifically for the orthorectification of HR and VHR optical and radar imagery. It is the most homogenous

and accurate elevation model, for orthorectification, on a global scale [RD-6]. The construction and specification of this resource is detailed in Table 4-2.

Table 4-2: Airbus WorldDem4Ortho Information

Parameter		Value
File Format		GeoTIFF
Data Type		32 Bit, floating
No Data Value		-32767.0
Geographic Coordinate Reference System	Horizontal	WGS84-G1150
	Vertical	EGM2008
Pixel Spacing		0.8 arcsec (approx. 24.0 m)
Absolute Vertical Accuracy ^{1, 2, 3}		< 4.0 m (LE@90)
Relative Vertical Accuracy ^{1, 2, 3}		< 2.0 m (slope ≤ 20 % LE@90) < 4.0 m (slope > 20 % LE@90) (90% linear point-to-point error within an area of 1° x 1°)
Absolute Horizontal Accuracy ^{2, 3}		< 6.0 m (CE@90)

1. Excluding urban areas (approximately levelled down to ground level and so are “DTM-like”).
2. Excluding area of Antarctica and Greenland.
3. Due to global coverage of the WorldDEM (radar data acquired during the TanDEM-X mission), all accuracy statistics and values sated here are calculated as an arithmetic mean on global level. Local deviations occur.

4.2.2 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy

4.2.2.1 Description I (Panchromatic Imagery)

The absolute geolocation (planimetric / horizontal) accuracy of the orthorectified panchromatic imagery is assessed using a method that directly determines the difference between the ‘absolute’ (actual) and apparent location of a set of ground control points (**GCPS**), defined by Global Positioning System (**GPS**) during a number of field surveys, in an image.

This assessment was performed on the following products:

La Crau (France)

Product 1: VIS1_BUN_20191208094350_ORTP_S89361_0915

Product 2: VIS1_BUN_20200212094124_ORTP_S91372_0c54

Product 3: VIS1_BUN_20201019094553_ORTP_S100955_19a8

The orthorectified imagery included in these three products have been used to determine the geolocation accuracy of *relatively low and homogenous topographies*. Note the topography of La Crau does not exceed 190 m above the ellipsoid.

Piedmont (Italy)

Product 4: VIS1_BUN_20200726093423_ORTP_S96522_1524

Product 5: VIS1_BUN_20200726093423_ORTP_S96581_1524

The orthorectified imagery included in these two products have been used to determine the geolocation accuracy of *relatively high and inhomogeneous topographies* where the 'orthorectification power' of the implemented processing is also determined. Note the topography of Piedmont does not exceed 910 m above the ellipsoid.

The determined absolute planimetric geolocation accuracies will be evaluated against the minimum requirement, which is specified as **< 12.0 m CE90 (at Nadir)**. Note it is common for the latter to be described as a circular error at a specified percentile (e.g. CE90 means that a minimum of 90 % of the points measured have an error that is less than the stated CE90 value).

Note Easting Direction / Pixel / Across-Track and Northing Direction / Line / Along-Track

4.2.2.2 Results

4.2.2.2.1 La Crau

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of the sensor's panchromatic imagery of La Crau is determined by this assessment as (average) 3.24 m RMSE and 4.20 m CE90, and so satisfies the minimum requirement specified previously. This result is detailed in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3: Vision-1: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy Results – La Crau

Parameter	Product 1: Value	Product 2: Value	Product 3: Value
Viewing Angle (°)	3.77	3.94	1.66
GCP Sample #	12	12	13
Mean Easting Error (m)	1.71	1.09	0.37
Mean Northing Error (m)	0.09	0.87	0.95
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	1.71	1.55	2.04
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	1.94	2.47	2.48
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	2.42	1.89	2.08
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	1.64	1.14	0.84
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	1.94	2.61	2.65
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	1.84	1.11	0.55
Root Mean Square Error (m)	3.10	3.23	3.37
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	3.94	4.33	4.33
Circular Error @ 90% (m) Metadata*	3.73	2.41	1.49

* Airbus One Atlas Basemap Ground Control Points Product 1 (111), Product 2 (440), Product 3 (9)

The number, density and distribution of the GCPs used in this assessment are shown in Figure 4-1.

It is important to note that the geolocation accuracy detailed in the product metadata are calculated with respect to reference data used and so is not the absolute (i.e. not directly comparable).

Figure 4-1: The number, density and distribution of GCPs (+,+) used to determine the absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of panchromatic imagery in Product 1 (left) and Product 2 (right). Product 3 is not shown here.

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy determined by this assessment is shown in Figure 4-2. The observed bias (mean error, systematic error contribution), in both directions, is consistently small (i.e. in the order of a pixel to sub-pixel) but the observed precision (standard deviation, random error contribution) is consistently (relatively) high (i.e. in the order of two to three pixels) which results in the slight degradation of the absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy determined here.

Figure 4-2: Absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy assessment of panchromatic imagery in Product 1 (Left), Product 2 (Middle), Product 3 (Right). (Key: ● GCP, - CE@90).

4.2.2.2.2 Piedmont

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of the sensor’s panchromatic imagery of Piedmont is determined by this assessment as 5.12 m RMSE and 5.50 m CE90, and so satisfies the minimum requirement specified previously. This result is detailed in Table 4-4.

Table 4-4: Vision-1: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy Results – Piedmont

Parameter	Product 4: Value	Product 5: Value
Viewing Angle (°)	1.21	
Ground Control Points Sample #	21	
Mean Easting Error (m)	1.56	
Mean Northing Error (m)	-3.12	
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	2.23	
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	2.09	
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	3.49	
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	2.11	1.45
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	3.75	
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	2.28	1.76
Root Mean Square Error (m)	5.12	
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	5.50	
Circular Error @ 90% (m) Metadata*	4.71	3.44

* Airbus One Atlas Basemap Ground Control Points Product 4 (472), Ground control points Product 5 (469)

The number, density and distribution of the GCPs used in this assessment are shown in Figure 4-3.

Figure 4-3: The number, density and distribution of GCPs (+) used to determine the absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of sequential acquisitions of panchromatic imagery in Product 4 (top) stitched to Product 5 (bottom).

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of the GCPs used in this assessment are shown in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-4: Absolute geolocation accuracy assessment of panchromatic imagery in Product 4 and 5 (● GCP, - CE@90).

Note the observed bias and precision, in both directions, is relatively moderate (i.e. in the order of two to four pixels) which results in the slight degradation of the absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy determined here. The latter is most likely due to the following factor:

- The bias and precision associated with the measured, absolute location of the ground control points identified during the field surveys of this challenging topography are degraded.

The degradation of absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy is commonly observed in very high-resolution imagery that has been processed using resources that are not of an appropriate spatial resolution or accuracy (usually due to the costs involved). However, this is unlikely to be the case here as the resources used are, as mentioned earlier, specifically designed for very high-resolution missions such as this one.

4.2.2.3 Description II (Multispectral Imagery)

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of the sensor’s multispectral imagery cannot be assessed using the same method adopted for the panchromatic imagery (i.e. the direct method) due to a lower spatial resolution. Instead, the in-direct method is used and this involves using another form of the aforementioned intensity-based image-matching algorithm (zero mean normalised cross-correlation, validated sub-pixel / 0.2 m accuracy), provided by the open-source CNES MEDICIS / QPEC tool [RD-8], between the sensor’s multispectral imagery and (actual) reference imagery from a similar sensor.

This assessment was performed on the following product:

Salon-de-Provence (France)

Product 6: VIS1_BUN_20201018094006_ORTP_S100933_199a (red band)

Reference Product: <SPOT 5 20121008T093232>

(Provided by CNES: Absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy is 2.5 m RMSE.)

4.2.2.4 Results II

4.2.2.4.1 Salon-de-Provence

The absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy of the sensor's multispectral imagery of Salon-de-Provence is determined by this assessment as 7.61 m RMSE and 12.07 m CE90 (detailed in Table 4-5). This absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy is good, especially when the viewing angle and accuracy of the orthorectified multispectral reference imagery used for the intensity-based image matching are taken into consideration.

**Table 4-5: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy: Vision-1 (Product 6) and SPOT 5
(Image Matching Confidence Level (CL@95%))**

Parameter	Product 6
Viewing Angle (°)	10.48
Number of Pixels	6875
Number of Pixels Matched	1831
Mean Easting Error (m)	4.46
Mean Northing Error (m)	0.12
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	5.26
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	3.22
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	6.90
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	2.17
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	3.22
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m) Metadata*	1.50
Root Mean Square Error (m)	7.61
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	12.07
Circular Error @ 90% (m) Metadata*	3.94

* Airbus One Atlas Basemap Ground Control Points Product 6 (11)

(Note the data provider has confirmed that although few GCPs were used for the refinement of this spread, the distribution across the imagery is good).

As mentioned previously, the relative planimetric geolocation accuracy detailed in the product metadata is determined with respect to the geolocation accuracy of the reference data used for geometric refinement only (how the geolocation accuracy varies with location is not yet known by the data provider). However, the result determined by this assessment is close to an estimate of the absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy that would be determined by the data provider if a combination of product and reference data (including SPOT imagery) geolocation accuracies are performed.

The results of the intensity-based image matching are shown in Figure 5-5 and Figure 4-6; Figure 4-6 shows that the areas of concentrated high circular errors are in the hilly areas of the region and this is most likely due to the resource used to orthorectify the reference imagery originally. Note it is also important to consider the limitations of using density-based image matching algorithms which include differences in viewing geometries, solar geometries (e.g. shadow), ground conditions (wet or dry ground), atmospheric conditions, and time elapsed between compared imagery.

Figure 4-5: Intensity-based image matching tool results for Vision-1 and reference SPOT 5 imagery. Note the absolute planimetric accuracy of SPOT 5 is 2.5 m.

Figure 4-6: The radial error disparity layer is placed on top of the multispectral imagery to help identify the areas in which high circular errors (i.e. dark pixels) are found. Note pixels with a no data value or radial error = 0 are transparent. (- top border of SPOT 5 imagery)

This latter can also be visually assessed using compressed and converted to grey-scale checkerboard versions of the product's multispectral imagery overlaying reference imagery (i.e. reference layer provided by Google Hybrid), as shown in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-7: Product 6: The modified checkerboard multispectral image layer, laid on top of the Google Hybrid reference layer, indicates good absolute planimetric geolocation accuracy. Scale 1:8700.

4.2.3 Temporal Geolocation Accuracy

4.2.3.1 Description

The temporal planimetric geolocation accuracy (i.e. stability) of multispectral and panchromatic imagery is determined by comparing imagery, using the intensity-based image algorithm described in Section 4.2.2.3, from products sensed at different points in time. Note no minimum requirement has been specified for temporal planimetric geolocation accuracy.

This assessment was performed on the following products:

Product 1 and Product 3

4.2.3.2 Results

Table 4-6: Temporal Planimetric Geolocation Accuracy (La Crau) – Pair Product 1 and 3

Parameter	IMAGE MATCHING (Confidence Level 95 %)	
	PAN (P1 – P3)	MS (red band) (P1-3)
Number of Matched Pixels	44652	2795
Mean Easting Error (m)	-1.64	-1.96
Mean Northing Error (m)	-1.97	-2.57
Easting Error Standard Deviation (m)	1.17	1.86
Northing Error Standard Deviation (m)	0.88	1.80
Easting Root Mean Square Error (m)	2.02	2.70
Northing Root Mean Square Error (m)	2.16	3.14
Root Mean Square Error (m)	2.95	4.14
Circular Error @ 90% (m)	4.08	6.15

The results indicate stability as the temporal planimetric geolocation accuracy of the multispectral imagery is 4.14 m RMSE (6.15 m CE90) and 4.08 m RMSE (2.95 m) for the panchromatic imagery. Note there is no minimum requirement specified.

4.2.4 Band Co-registration Accuracy

4.2.4.1 Description

The multispectral and panchromatic band co-registration accuracies have been determined using the aforementioned intensity-based image matching algorithm, where it was applied to the imagery of each pair of adjacent bands (e.g. blue (**band 1**) and green (**band 2**), green and red (**band 3**), red and near-infrared (**band 4**), near-infrared and panchromatic (**band 5**), and panchromatic and blue).

The results of this assessment will be evaluated against the minimum requirement, which is as follows:

- **Multispectral Band Co-registration Accuracy < 0.3 MS (1.044 m) pixels CE90**
- **Multispectral-Panchromatic Band Co-registration Accuracy < 0.3 MS (1.044 m) pixels CE90**

This measurement is important to the generation of the sensor's pan-sharpened imagery, (the fusion of multispectral and panchromatic imagery, resulting in imagery with an increased spatial and spectral resolution).

This assessment was performed on the following products:

Product 1, Product 2 and Product 3

4.2.4.2 Results

The results of this assessment, detailed in Table 4-7, indicate the following band co-registration accuracies (averaged for the three products assessed):

- **Multispectral Band Co-registration**
 - **Band1_2 CE@90 = 0.22 MS Pixels**
 - **Band2_3 CE@90 = 0.23 MS Pixels**
 - **Band3_4 CE@90 = 0.36 MS Pixels**
- **Multispectral-Panchromatic Band Co-registration**
 - **Band4_5 CE@90 = 0.55 MS Pixels**
 - **Band5_1 CE@90 = 0.40 MS Pixels**

Note: the pixel size of panchromatic imagery is resampled (cubic interpolation resampling kernel) to match that of the multispectral imagery.

Table 4-7: La Crau: Multispectral and Panchromatic Band Co-registration Accuracy (Image Matching Confidence Level @ 95 %). Units: Multispectral Pixels.

	Multispectral			Multispectral - Panchromatic		
	Band Pair: 1_2	Band Pair: 2_3	Band Pair: 3_4	Band Pair: 4_5	Band Pair: 5_1	
Product 1						
Number of Matched Pixel Total	2242	4023	430	758	3096	
Mean Easting Error (px)	-0.002	-0.009	0.046	0.0837	0.0756	0.119
Mean Northing Error (px)	0.013	-0.082	0.061	-0.0381	-0.0379	-0.045
Easting Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.082	0.075	0.108	0.1746	0.1540	
Northing Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.109	0.107	0.181	0.2259	0.1649	
Easting Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.082	0.075	0.117	0.193	0.171	
Northing Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.110	0.135	0.191	0.229	0.169	

Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.137	0.155	0.225	0.299	0.240	
Circular Error @ 90% Confidence (m)	0.221	0.225	0.365	0.477	0.371	
Product 2						
Number of Matched Pixel Total	3384	5149	330	424	4068	
Mean Easting Error (px)	0.005	0.002	0.028	0.0624	0.0488	0.098
Mean Northing Error (px)	0.021	-0.066	0.047	-0.0469	-0.0252	-0.045
Easting Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.088	0.075	0.106	0.1937	0.1429	
Northing Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.095	0.097	0.152	0.2767	0.1520	
Easting Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.088	0.075	0.110	0.203	0.151	
Northing Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.097	0.118	0.159	0.280	0.154	
Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.131	0.140	0.194	0.346	0.215	
Circular Error @ 90% Confidence (m)	0.210	0.227	0.325	0.540	0.333	
Product 3						
Number of Matched Pixel Total	4191	5600	700	5923	4457	
Mean Easting Error (px)	-0.006	0.002	0.035	-0.145	-0.196	-0.114
Mean Northing Error (px)	0.012	-0.059	0.053	-0.226	-0.207	-0.219
Easting Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.092	0.075	0.138	0.210	0.131	
Northing Error Standard Deviation (px)	0.098	0.108	0.164	0.251	0.136	
Easting Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.092	0.075	0.143	0.255	0.235	
Northing Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.099	0.123	0.172	0.337	0.247	
Root Mean Square Error (px)	0.136	0.144	0.224	0.423	0.341	
Circular Error @ 90% Confidence (m)	0.216	0.236	0.376	0.642	0.486	

The band co-registration error of the multispectral blue-green and green-red bands lie within the minimum requirement specified but the co-registration error of the red-near-infrared bands lie just above. The co-registration error of the multispectral-panchromatic bands lie above the minimum requirement but this is most likely due to the error introduced when geometric downsampling the panchromatic image to be used in panchromatic-multispectral image matching.

In addition to the latter, the error budget has been calculated for each product (as shown in the last six cells of Table Table 4-7), and is low (i.e. supports good band co-registration accuracies); the error budget rule is that per pixel displacement errors are transitive across all band pairs. By summing displacement for these band pairs (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4) and (4, 5), the result is in the same order of displacement for the twin (1, 5), as shown in the equation below.

$$D_{1,5} \cong D_{1,2} + D_{2,3} + D_{3,4} + D_{4,5}$$

Where $D_{B,p}$ stands for displacement between the band 1 (blue) and the band 5 (panchromatic) in both easting and northing directions.

4.3 Radiometric Calibration Quality

The radiometric calibration, or correction, of sensor data sees to the successful conversion of raw data (i.e. digital numbers) to spectral radiance or reflectance, using coefficients (e.g. physical bias, physical gain, solar spectral irradiance constants) derived pre-flight in laboratory conditions. This is important as it improves the interpretability and quality of the sensor data (and is particularly important when comparing multiple sensor datasets over a period of time, which is commonly performed by the scientific community).

The digital number (DN) to spectral radiance (L) conversion of sensor data, per band (b, see Table 4-8) is enabled by the following:

$$L_b = DN_b * GAIN_b + BIAS_b$$

The spectral radiance (L_b) to top-of-atmosphere reflectance (ρ_b), per band (b) is enabled by the following:

$$\rho_b = \frac{\pi * L_b * d^2}{E_{0b} * \cos(\theta_s)} = \frac{\text{Radiation (radiation leaving the Earth)}}{\text{Irradiance (Radiation reaching the earth from the Sun)}}$$

Where:

E_{0b} is solar spectral irradiance at the sensor for band b (units: $Wm^{-2}\mu m^{-1}$).

θ_s is solar zenith angle at the time / location of acquisition (units: degrees).

d^2 is Sun-Earth distance at the time of acquisition (units: astronomical units).

Note all coefficients mentioned above can be found in the product user guide, the product metadata and online.

Table 4-8: Characteristics of Vision-1 Spectral Bands

Band	Wavelength λ (nm)	Centre Wavelength λ (nm)
Panchromatic	450 - 650	550
Blue	440 - 510	475
Green	510 - 590	550
Red	600 - 670	635
NIR	760 - 910	835

This section describes the assessment of radiometric calibration quality of sensor products, in terms of **absolute** and **temporal radiometric calibration accuracy**.

4.3.1 Absolute Radiometric Calibration Accuracy

4.3.1.1 Description I

The method used to determine the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy of the sensor's bands is based on comparing the top-of-atmosphere reflectance values derived from the sensors acquisitions of the chosen RadCalNet calibration sites with the top-of-atmosphere reflectance values derived from the RadCalNet calibration sites themselves (i.e. reference top-of-atmosphere reflectance values).

The RadCalNet calibration sites, operated by the CEOS Working Group for Calibration and Validation (**WGCV**) Infrared and Visible Optical Sensors (**IVOS**), provides the scientific community with the following:

- Top-of-atmosphere reflectance values, derived from both in-situ surface and atmosphere measurements (e.g. surface pressure, columnar water vapour, columnar ozone, aerosol optical depth, etc.) that are **SI-traceable**, at:
 - 30-minute intervals between 09:00 and 15:00 local standard time (cloud-free data only), and 10 nm spectral sample intervals between 400 nm and 1000 nm.

Note the RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance values are representative of nadir viewing observations only, so comparison to sensor top-of-atmosphere reflectance values should be used with caution - when the sensor viewing zenith angle deviates significantly from nadir, both atmospheric and surface non-Lambertian behaviour can lead to significant deviation from at-nadir simulated signal. The correction for the latter (i.e. off-nadir viewing angle effects), as well as illumination (solar) angle effects, can be done using bi-directional reflectance modelling.

The products used to assess the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy, by temporal and spatial simulation with RadCalNet data, are the following:

La Crau (France)

Product 1: VIS1_BUN_20191208094350_ORTP_S89361_0915

Gobabeb Desert (Namibia)

Product 7: VIS1_BUN_20200919094629_ORTP_S99144_180c

Product 8: VIS1_BUN_20200920095214_ORTP_S99149_181b

These products provide acquisitions of the chosen RadCalNet calibration sites, La Crau (see Table 4-9, Figure 4-8) and Gobabeb (see Table 4-10, Figure 4-9).

Table 4-9: RadCalNet La Crau Calibration Site Description

Parameter	Description
Geographic Location	Latitude: 43.558889, Longitude: 4.864167, Altitude: 20 m
Characteristics	The RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra are representative of a disk of 30 m radius.

Table 4-10: RadCalNet Gobabeb Calibration Site Description

Parameter	Description
Geographic Location	Latitude: -23.6002, Longitude: 15.1196, Altitude: 510 m
Characteristics	The RadCalNet top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra are representative of a disk of 30 m radius.

The determined absolute radiometric calibration accuracies will be evaluated against the minimum requirement, which is specified as **red / green / blue < 5.9 %**, **near-infrared < 6.2 %** and **panchromatic < 6 %**. Note these requirements were determined after a number

of initial on-ground and in-orbit calibration procedures and measurements but the operator plans to perform further in-orbit measurements to ensure continued image data quality throughout the lifetime of Vision-1.

Figure 4-8: The La Crau RadCalNet Site and Region of Interest used.

Figure 4-9: The Gobabeb RadCalNet Site and Region of Interest used.

4.3.1.2 Results I

The results of this assessment can be found in Table 4-12 -
 Table 4-14.

Table 4-11: Vision-1 Sensor Observation Conditions (Solar and Viewing Geometries)

Product	Sensor Viewing Angle (°)	Sensor Incidence Angle (°)	Sensor Azimuth Angle (°)	Solar Elevation Angle (°)	Solar Azimuth Angle (°)	Water Vapour (g/cm)	AOD ()
1	3.785	4.141	-104.187	19.220	153.608	1.22	0.052
7	5.518	6.025	82.574	60.363	35.440	1.27	0.150
8	8.813	9.627	-99.780	61.475	33.100	1.16	0.071

Note the absolute radiometric accuracy was calculated without **bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF)** corrections (*wbc) and then with corrections, for an

interesting comparison, but only for the blue, green, red and near-infrared bands of Product 7 and 8. The corrections were not deemed necessary for Product 1 whose viewing angle is below 5°.

Table 4-12: La Crau: Vision-1 and Simulated Vision -1 (RadCalNet) TOA Reflectances

Product	Origin	ρ TOA Reflectance				
		Blue	Green	Red	NIR	PAN
1	Sensor	0.1402273	0.1121020	0.1010856	0.1960118	0.1200545
	Sensor (wbc)	-	-	-	-	-
	RadCalNet	0.1472999	0.1145908	0.1024096	0.1893577	0.1188363

Table 4-13: Gobabeb: Vision-1 and Simulated Vision -1 (RadCalNet) TOA Reflectances

Product	Origin	ρ TOA Reflectance				
		Blue	Green	Red	NIR	PAN
7	Sensor	0.1978530	0.2245754	0.2871993	0.3140815	0.2401791
	Sensor (wbc)	0.1926355	0.2228540	0.2858177	0.3123814	-
	RadCalNet	0.1985530	0.2884707	0.2977468	0.3317590	0.2389329
8	Sensor	0.1862748	0.2173184	0.2809274	0.3090687	0.2281065
	Sensor (wbc)	0.1939692	0.2236320	0.2864846	0.3129371	-
	RadCalNet	0.1966055	0.2288347	0.2992070	0.3347000	0.2390945

The difference, expressed as a percentage, between Vision-1 top-of-atmosphere reflectances ($\rho_b work$) and simulated Vision-1 top-of-atmosphere reflectances ($\rho_b simulated$) is calculated as follows:

$$\rho_b = ((\rho_b simulated - \rho_b work) / (\rho_b simulated)) * 100$$

Table 4-14: Comparison between Vision-1 and Simulated Vision-1 RadCalNet TOA Reflectances

Product	ρ TOA Reflectance Difference (%)				
	Blue	Green	Red	NIR	PAN
1	4.80	2.95	1.29	-3.51	-1.02
7	0.35	1.70	3.54	5.33	-0.52
8	5.25	5.03	6.11	7.66	4.59

Table 4-15: Comparison between BRDF-corrected Vision-1 and Simulated Vision-1 RadCalNet TOA Reflectances

Product	ρ TOA Reflectance Difference (%)				
	Blue	Green	Red	NIR	PAN
1	-	-	-	-	-
7	2.98	2.46	4.01	5.84	-
8	1.34	2.27	4.25	6.50	-

These results indicate the **absolute radiometric accuracy** of all Vision-1 bands are very well calibrated and **meet the minimum requirements**.

Figure 4-10: La Crau: Absolute Radiometric Accuracy : Vision-1 TOA-Reflectance vs. Simulated Vision-1 RadCalNet TOA-Reflectance (- 1:1 Comparison).

Figure 4-11: Gobabeb: Absolute Radiometric Accuracy: Vision-1 TOA-Reflectance vs. Simulated RadCalNet TOA-Reflectance (- 1:1 Comparison).

4.3.1.3 Description II

The alternative method used to determine the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy of the sensor was based on comparing top-of-atmosphere reflectance values of the sensor's acquisitions of a suitable calibration site with top-of-atmosphere reflectance values from a well-calibrated sensor of the same site (i.e. cross-calibration method). Note the well-

calibrated sensor used here was that of the **Sentinel-2B's Multispectral Instrument (MSI)** sensor whose **absolute radiometric accuracy**, determined regularly for all multispectral bands, is $< 3\% \pm 2\%$ [RD-11].

The aforementioned alternative method is broken down into the following stages:

1. Create a reference surface reflectance (bottom-of-atmosphere) time-series of chosen calibration site, using reference data from Sentinel-2B MSI Level 2A Surface Reflectance products that correspond to acquisitions during 2019 / 2020 (e.g. MGRS tile 34RGS).
2. Assess the reference surface reflectance time-series for directional effects (i.e. create a model that can then be used to correct Vision-1 data for directional effects).
3. Apply spectral interpolation, with a step of 2 nm, to the surface reflectance given at each Sentinel-2 band central wavelength (i.e. bottom-of-atmosphere spectrum (where the spectrum is the dependence of reflectance on wavelength)).
4. Considering the Vision-1 product observation date, observation geometry and the location of the calibration site, collect the data of the required atmospheric parameters from the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service.
5. With the Vision-1 product observation geometry and atmospheric parameters, apply the 6S Atmospheric Radiative Transfer Model to estimate the top-of-atmosphere spectrum (2 nm) from the bottom-of-atmosphere spectrum.
6. Extract the region-of-interest, defined for the chosen calibration site, from selected Vision-1 acquisitions. Convert from digital numbers to top-of-atmosphere reflectances using the calibration coefficients provided by the data provider.
7. Convolve the top-of-atmosphere spectrum with the Vision-1 spectral response to obtain simulated top-of-atmosphere reflectance values at the central wavelength of each Vision-1 band. Note the relative spectral responses for this sensor are available upon request from the data provider.

The calibration site used was one of the most popular Pseudo-Invariant Calibration Site(s) (**PICS**), defined by the CEOS WGCV and IVOS, known as **Libya-4** (28.55° N and 23.39° E). The calibration site, which over the last four decades has consistently demonstrated its suitability for the radiometric calibration and validation of very high to low resolution optical sensors, is a radiometrically bright (i.e. high and near-Lambertian reflectance) site that importantly exhibits reasonable **spatial**, **spectral** and **temporal uniformity**, as well as optimal **atmospheric conditions** (e.g. low aerosol loading, cloud-free skies).

The products used include the following:

Libya-4 (Libya, Africa)

Product 9: VIS1_BUN_20191214083816_ORTP_S91223_0982

Product 10: VIS1_BUN_20191215084401_ORTP_S90943_0990

Reference Product: (Reference Mission – Sentinel-2B)

4.3.1.4 Results II

The results, detailed in Table 4-17, indicate that the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy of all Vision-1 multispectral bands are within 3.2 % of Sentinel-2B MSI's and therefore confirms that all multispectral bands are well calibrated and meet the **minimum requirement specified**.

In Figure 4-12 and Figure 4-13, the top-of-atmosphere reflectances detailed above, which have been obtained from the imagery of Libya-4, are plotted as a function of wavelength as well as the relative spectral response.

Table 4-16: Vision-1 Sensor Observation Conditions (Solar and Viewing Geometries)

Product	Sensor Viewing Angle (°)	Sensor Incidence Angle (°)	Sensor Azimuth Angle (°)	Solar Elevation Angle (°)	Solar Azimuth Angle (°)
9	5.804	6.348	82.563	32.623	151.810
10	7.500	8.204	-99.780	33.149	153.130

Table 4-17: Vision-1 Radiometric Cross-Calibration with Sentinel-2B MSI

Product	Band Name	Central Wavelength (nm)	ρ TOA Sentinel-2	ρ TOA Vision-1	ρ Sentinel-2 / Vision-1	ρ Difference (%)
9	Blue	476.0	0.250	0.247	1.012	1.20
	Green	549.0	0.314	0.311	1.010	1.03
	Red	635.0	0.413	0.420	0.982	-1.80
	NIR	836.0	0.513	0.501	1.024	2.38
10	Blue	476.0	0.253	0.248	1.019	1.88
	Green	549.0	0.313	0.313	1.000	0.03
	Red	635.0	0.409	0.422	0.969	-3.18
	NIR	836.0	0.517	0.515	1.005	0.49

Figure 4-12: Vision-1 spectral response with top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectrum for Libya-4. Product 9.

Figure 4-13: Vision-1 spectral response with top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectrum for Libya-4. Product 10.

4.3.2 Temporal Radiometric Accuracy

4.3.2.1 Description

The temporal radiometric accuracy is determined by producing a time-series of mean top-of-atmosphere reflectance, calculated for the defined area of interest (Figure 4-14), against the number of days since launch.

This assessment was performed on the following products:

Libya-4 (Libya, Africa)

Product 9

Product 10

Product 11: S1000cb7-L1 (20200220084715)

Product 12: S1000be2-L1 (20200203084503)

(Note the last two orthorectified products do not conform to the official naming convention used by the first two as they were packaged differently).

Figure 4-14: Product 10: The mean top-of-atmosphere reflectance of pixels enclosed by the region of interest (-, 0.1° (Latitude) x 0.1° (Longitude)), is used to measure radiometric geolocation accuracy of Vision-1 data.

4.3.2.2 Results

The results of this assessment are shown in Figure 4-15. The linear regression model suggests radiometric stability for all multispectral bands over the period observed but confirmation of this can only be achieved by the assessment of more products (the data provider confirmed all relevant products archived were supplied).

Figure 4-15: The radiometric stability of each spectral band (the mean top-of-atmosphere reflectance vs. days since launch, for Products 9 – 12).

Note there is no minimum requirement specified for temporal radiometric accuracy.

4.4 Image Quality

This section describes the assessment of product image quality on the supplied sensor products in terms of **Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)**, **Modulation Transfer Function (MTF)** and **Image Interpretability**.

4.4.1 Signal-to-Noise Ratio

4.4.1.1 Description

The SNR is used to quantify the performance of a sensor in response to a particular exposure; it quantifies the ratio of the sensor's output signal to the noise present in the output signal and can be expressed by the following:

$$SNR = \frac{\mu}{\sigma}$$

Where μ is the mean signal and σ is the standard deviation of the signal.

This assessment was performed on the following products:

Libya-4 (Libya, Africa)

Product 9: VIS1_BUN_20191214083816_ORTP_S91223_0982

Product 10: VIS1_BUN_20191215084401_ORTP_S90943_0990

Product 11: S1000cb7-L1 (20200220084715)

The method proposed for this assessment allows for the estimation of (spatial) SNR, based on the aforementioned equation and the following assumption:

- The mean signal is defined as the spatial average of a group of pixels observing a spatially varying scene and the noise is defined as the standard deviation of this signal for the same group of pixels.

The method, modified since it was initially proposed in [RD-6], is performed for each spectral band, whose imagery has been converted from digital numbers to radiance, in the following way:

1. Compute the local statistics of a small (3 x 3 pixels) sliding window applied to the imagery being assessed. Select only the "best" small windows for the following steps.
 - a. The selection of small windows ensures that increased site uniformity is generally maintained (if not, where spatially high frequencies exist (e.g. sharp transitions seen as dune summits, dedicated image processing is applied in order to detect this and filter (e.g. Sobel Filter)).
2. Compute the statistical distribution (histogram), between the **minimum** and **maximum radiance**, of the selected "best" small windows (statistics of 3 x 3 pixel windows) – the

signal is defined as the peak (i.e. mean radiance) of this statistical distribution and the noise is defined as the standard deviation of this statistical distribution about the mean.

3. Estimate SNR(s).
 - a. The most accurate estimations of SNR are derived from statistical distributions that are of a normal (i.e. Gaussian) nature.

The estimated SNR, including that from quantisation, for each band will be evaluated against the expected performance specified in Table 4-18 [RD-3].

Table 4-18: Vision-1 SNR Specification

Band	Mean Radiance (W.m ⁻² .str ⁻¹)	SNR
Blue	167.1	228.5
Green	143.8	258.6
Red	122.3	231.2
NIR	72.2	225.3
PAN	149.0	247.2

Please note that SNR is an important image quality indicator - high SNRs are required in order to control uncertainties in radiometric measurements, especially multispectral bands, as much as possible.

Note: These ratios have only been estimated for a bright target but it would have been interesting to see how these ratios compared to those estimated for a dark target (e.g. large body of water).

4.4.1.2 Results

The results of this assessment are detailed in Table 4-19.

Table 4-19: Vision-1 SNR

Band	Product 9		Product 10		Product 11	
	Mean Radiance W.m ⁻² .str ⁻¹	SNR	Mean Radiance W.m ⁻² .str ⁻¹	SNR	Mean Radiance W.m ⁻² .str ⁻¹	SNR
Blue	86.95	162.31	85.66	157.72	103.68	176.14
Green	99.81	133.88	98.22	130.75	124.69	152.12
Red	119.04	112.76	116.60	108.33	145.22	122.68
NIR	90.33	107.40	91.16	106.75	108.72	119.11
PAN	103.62	220.63	102.29	212.77	129.95	233.09

Figure 4-16: SNR: Example Vision-1 Product 11 Red band.

The results indicate above satisfactory and stable SNR values for all multispectral and panchromatic bands but they cannot be easily compared with the SNR values given in the specification (see Table 4-18) as the mean radiance for each band is different (the target used is unknown) and method used is most likely different.

4.4.2 Modulation Transfer Function

4.4.2.1 Description

The spatial resolution of a sensor has traditionally been a difficult concept to define, but all would agree that it is inextricably linked to the GSD and Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) of an imaging sensor system.

As a measure of the geospatial quality of imagery, the MTF of the system is often used along with the SNR. The MTF is often used as a measure of image sharpness. This important parameter for image quality has to be checked on each orbit in order to be sure that launch vibrations, transition from air to vacuum, or thermal state have not degraded the sharpness of the images [RD-12].

4.4.2.1.1 Methods and Tools

The slant-edge method presented herein has been developed and operated in the context of the ESA contribution to the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency's ALOS PRISM calibration campaign [RD-13]. The different steps of the algorithm are depicted within Figure 4-17 below and discussed thereafter.

Figure 4-17: Slant-edge method – algorithm steps.

The input MTF target is a checkboard image observed in the panchromatic and illustrated in Figure 4-18 and Figure 4-19. The region of interest includes edge transitions, and nearly-vertical / nearly-horizontal edges are used to estimate MTF in the Along-track (AL) / Across-track (AC) direction or axis.

The method estimates for any spectral channels the MTF associated with the complete system response. The MTF is derived from computation of the ESF and Line Spread Function (LSF). These curves are accompanied with quality indicator metrics, such as Relative Edge Response (RER), SNR and Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM).

Edge Modelling

The true MTF is defined normal to the edge. If the edge is slanted, MTF is calculated from the average of many sampling phases.

The construction of the ESF is inspired from [RD-14] where sampling phases are collected for a given orientation of the target. The Edge modelling step is the estimation of the orientation of the target. As shown in Figure 4-18, for each image row included in the region depicted with rectangular form (upper left image), a parametric function is fitted in order to estimate the sub-pixel location of the inflection point. Based on the set of inflection point sub-pixel location found, a least square method is used to estimate an overall orientation angle (upper right image). The per-row interpolated edge functions (lower left image) are checked and discarded in case of noise. In the figure below (lower left image), it is observed that the form of the curve changes depending on the image row.

Figure 4-18: Slant-edge method – edge modelling output and estimation of orientation angle.

Edge Spread Function Construction

The MTF method is very sensitive to noise and the orientation of edge should be accurately known. As mentioned before, a single image row is not sufficient to capture the various pixel phases accounting for aliasing and phase effects etc. The super resolved target image is built applying the same approach for each image row and following these stages;

- Projection of each image pixel onto a line perpendicular to edge applying rotation angle estimate in the previous step, the method proposed by Kohm [RD-14] is used;
- Resampling of the pixel position in the new projection system, within bin of $\frac{1}{4}$ pixel width.

Figure 4-19 shows the super resolved target image with edge transitions that are now perfectly aligned. Depending on the expected direction (Along / Across axis), it is possible to define for each bin, the intensity value (pixel phase) of the ESF. By nature, in the final ESF, some bins can be left empty. It is therefore important to maximize the number of processed lines over sample target are used.

Because some bins are left empty, at this point the sampling of the ESF data points are not uniformly distributed. The LOESS curve fitting algorithm (locally weighted non-parametric regression fitting using a 2nd order polynomial) is used to resample the data to uniformly spaced sample points. There is no a priori ESF model fit to the data points (parametric approach) as commonly done in the community.

Figure 4-19: Super Resolve Target (0.25 pixel bin).

MTF Calculation

The final stage is to compute MTF by using a derivative method: computing the finite difference approximation of the uniformly spaced ESF to produce the LSF.

The LSF may contain high frequency noise, amplified by the derivative method. A local smoothing with fourth order Savitsky Golay filtering is applied (window size is 11 bins) to remove outliers. At the end, a Hann window is applied to the ESF (three-term weighted average smoothing technique) and a smooth LSF is obtained.

The main outputs of the method are shown in Figure 4-20 below. The ESF, LSF and FTM curves are carefully checked. An additional figure (Lower left in the figure) is used to check LOESS interpolation and in particular intensity estimated for all empty bins.

Figure 4-20: (a) Standard outputs of the MTF methods, LSF produced with the first derivative of ESF curve.

4.4.2.1.2 Region of interest and Input dataset

This assessment was performed using an acquisition of an artificial edge target, dedicated to MTF assessments, located in Salon-de-Provence (France). The physical characteristics of this artificial edge target takes the form of a 2 x 2 (60 m x 60 m) painted checkerboard. An image of the MTF target is shown in Figure 4-21, it is observed that the uniform regions are not homogeneous, it is due to the ageing of the target that is not maintained anymore.

The convention used to report MTF assessment is as follows:

- VL – Down Along-track Edge, Vertical Edge from low to high luminance;
- VH – Up Along-track Edge, Vertical Edge from high to low luminance;
- HL – Right Across-track Edge, Horizontal Edge from low to high luminance;
- HH – Left Across-track Edge, Horizontal Edge from high to low luminance.

The product used for this assessment, which is the raw “L0Rp” product, is the following.

Product 12: S100199a1_002_2_L0R (panchromatic only)

The processing implemented for the generation of this product is basic and, more importantly, geometric resampling was not used. Note this product type was provided to the EDAP optical team for this assessment only.

Figure 4-21: An RGB image of the Salon-de-Provence Modulation Transfer Target.

4.4.2.1.3 Input Specification

The MTF requirements specified by the data provider are:

Satellite MTF per Band: MS: > 20%; PAN: > 10% (Minimum requirements)

4.4.2.2 Results

The orientation angle estimate provided very similar results; 11.77 degree which is good point. The orientation allows to define criteria regarding the over sampling factor. A value of 0.15 has been selected, the processing results was degraded by using a lower value as 0.1 because of noise.

The consistency of the method is evaluated against the SNR. The key image quality parameters are report in the table below; the FWHM, the RER and the MTF at Nyquist value, Nyquist spatial frequency defined as 0.5 cycle per pixel. The results are provided, according to conventions discussed above, the along-track MTF (AL MTF) for both Hh and Hl configurations, and the across-track MTF (AC MTF) for both VH and VI configurations.

The table below shows that results are coherent whatever the configurations; FWHM, RER, MTF results are very stable. The SNR of the method is low and it might be explained by the quality to the target. It can be noted a slight degradation of results regarding the Along Track MTF, particularly true for the RER, this is due the satellite motion.

Table 4-20: MTF Assessment Results (orientation 11.77°, sampling 0.15)

Direction	MTF (Along-track)		MTF (Across-track)	
	Hh	HI	Vh	VI
SNR	23.14	22.42	30.52	19.11
FWHM	1.65	1.80	1.65	1.50
RER	-4.55	4.54	-4.73	4.83
MTF@Nyquist	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.10

The MTF results for all directions (Hh, HI, Vh, VI) are shown in graphics below.

Figure 4-22: Vision-1 MTF Results.

Figure 4-23: Along-track MTF Assessment, Hh.

Figure 4-24: Along-track MTF Assessment, HI.

Figure 4-25: Across-track MTF Assessment, Vh.

Figure 4-26: Across-track MTF Assessment, VI.

Note the condition of imaging data needs to be taken into consideration: cloud, noise, product processing level, along or across direction of flight, viewing and illumination geometries, storage format, and size of target / spatial resolution relationship.

4.4.3 Image Interpretability

4.4.3.1 Description

The image interpretability of optical sensor imagery is an important aspect of image quality (originating from the actual sensor or image processing), especially in terms of their practical use or application. This is commonly assessed, subjectively, using a well-defined procedure that is based on the successful interpretation of objects or features according to

the National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale¹ (**NIIRS**) category in which the sensor belongs. This well-defined procedure also importantly allows for the cross-comparison of image quality from similar sensors.

The products used for this assessment are the following:

Salon-de-Provence (France)

Product 6: VIS1_BUN_20201018094006_ORTP_S100933_199a

Reference Product: < Pléiades >

The method used to assess image interpretability consists of clipping 100 x 100 pixel windows from the sensor's imagery (for each band), centred on the objects or features of interest. Note the reference imagery is processed in order to ensure the pixel size of the reference imagery matches that of this sensor's imagery.

The objects or features used for this assessment are defined in

Table 4-21. The latter are deemed suitable for **NIIRS Category 3 (2.5 – 4.5 m)** and **NIIRS Category 5 (0.75 – 1.2 m GSD)** [RD-3] imagery.

Table 4-21: Vision-1: Image Interpretability of Objects or Features of Interest in Salon-de-Provence

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (671090.3105554151115939 4830278.58671295549720526)	1	Modulation Transfer Function target
Point (671364.24309313111007214 4833044.0252351425588131)	2	Motor way / sharp transition (45° NE)
Point (668580.81736886233557016 4828965.45189037173986435)	3	Forest
Point (670056.62237295764498413 4828905.08180973120033741)	4	Roundabout / parking lot
Point (669985.90922565956134349 4832120.72269264236092567)	5	Elevated tree
Point (669956.03863696497865021 4832655.53592716064304113)	6	Motor way / roundabout
Point (670564.24590074480511248 4833363.40447467099875212)	7	The dam
Point (669836.88448120269458741 4832528.00618595350533724)	8	Big building (shadow)
Point (670518.95015854423400015 4829513.56928175128996372)	9	Landing track - 34
Point (670249.72702971810940653 4831735.0312919020652771)	10	Floor painting

¹ <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm>

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (670900.38168655894696712 4829617.21182315889745951)	11	Crop fields / sparse
Point (671548.0352310094749555 4830292.1131860688328743)	12	Broad-leaved woodland
Point (671099.93821095407474786 4828090.14610077627003193)	13	Crop fields
Point (671156.44116920174565166 4828825.77096180152148008)	14	Bridge and water
Point (671120.4438803291413933 4827691.31545618735253811)	15	Crop fields
Point (670328.31568091106601059 4831489.30539688002318144)	16	Building / EA 15
Point (671516.86161747551523149 4833207.41657157335430384)	17	Greenhouse
Point (669996.87127304612658918 4829099.09009433817118406)	18	Parking lot
Point (670062.87681329366751015 4829781.35287734866142273)	19	Plane parking
Point (670860.46870227111503482 4831527.10888031311333179)	20	Plane hangar
Point (671802.47347140731289983 4832385.40385554917156696)	21	Small crop fields
Point (671246.59432400949299335 4832300.03732818737626076)	22	Urban city

4.4.3.2 Results

Band PAN (Vision-1, Points 1 - 21)

(Note comparisons between the panchromatic bands of Pléiades and Vision-1 could not be made as Pléiades panchromatic imagery was not available for this assessment (the geometric upsampling of Pléiades multispectral imagery to the same pixel size as Vision-1 panchromatic would have introduced significant degradation to image quality.).)

Band 1 (Vision-1, Pléiades, Points 1 - 21)

Band 2 (Vision-1, Pléiades, Points 1 - 21)

Band 3 (Vision-1, Pléiades, Points 1 - 21)

Band 4 (Vision-1, Pléiades, Points 1 - 21)

The sensor's imagery appears to be of a good quality, especially when compared to the reference sensor's imagery, based on important factors such as improved contrast or improved delineation of objects or features of interest. Note the clear interpretation of some objects or features of interest are not possible due to the presence of saturation in the visible bands (see example and possible explanation in 4.5.2).

4.5 Visual Inspection

4.5.1 Description

General visual inspections were performed on the multispectral and panchromatic imagery included in a sample of products, in order to ensure there were no gross anomalies or artefacts were present. The results are detailed in Table 4-22.

4.5.2 Results

Table 4-22: Vision-1 Visual Inspection Results

Product	Visual Inspection Results	
1	There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).	
2	There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).	
3	There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).	
4	There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).	

5	<p>There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).</p>	
6	<p>There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).</p>	
7	<p>There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product.</p>	
8	-	-
9	<p>There appears to be no gross anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product.</p>	
10	<p>There appears to be no anomalies or artefacts observed in the imagery of this product. However, in the visible bands, it is worth noting that saturation occurs in the areas of the imagery that contain naturally smooth and / or bright surfaces (e.g. white surfaces, metal surfaces, etc.).</p> <p>The histogram shows that the blue band is saturated</p>	
11	-	-
12	(Non-orthorectified Product)	-
13	-	-

Figure 4-27 The visual inspection of Product 9 (left) and Product 10 (right) reveals three equidistant lines (only one shown above) that span from top to bottom of the imagery.

In the visual inspection of imagery, the existence of three, equidistant lines that spanned from top to bottom was noticed. This is not clearly visible in all imagery but the nature of these lines suggest that this might be due to the across-track array of charge-coupled devices on the focal plane.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This technical note details the high-level data quality assessments (including geometric calibration, radiometric calibration and image quality) that were performed on a sample of thirteen, **orthorectified Vision-1 bundle products**. The results of the aforementioned data quality assessments conclude that the **performance of the sensor and the processing implemented is good** and, more importantly, **conforms to the specification detailed by Airbus**.

APPENDIX A VISION-1 TEST DATASET

ID	Site	Product_Type	Product_Identifier
VIS.01	La Crau	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20191208094350_ORTP_S89361_0915
VIS.02	La Crau	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20200212094124_ORTP_S91372_0c54
VIS.03	La Crau	Ortho	VIS1_PAN_20201019094553_ORTP_S100955_19a8
VIS.04	Piedmont	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20200726093423_ORTP_S96522_1524
VIS.05	Piedmont	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20200726093423_ORTP_S96581_1524
VIS.06	Salon-de-Provence	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20201018094006_ORTP_S100933_199a
VIS.07	Gobabeb	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20200919094629_ORTP_S99144_180c
VIS.08	Gobabeb	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20200920095214_ORTP_S99149_181b
VIS.09	Libya-4	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20191214083816_ORTP_S91223_0982
VIS.10	Libya-4	Ortho	VIS1_BUN_20191215084401_ORTP_S90943_0990
VIS.11	Libya-4	Ortho	S1000cb7-L1 (20200220084715)
VIS.12	Salon-de-Provence	Raw	S100199aI_002_2_L0R
VIS.13	Libya-4	Ortho	S1000be2-L1 (20200203084503)

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